

Evaluating deformation-based parametrization of ocean mesoscale eddies using eddy geometry approach

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Abstract

This is the abstract.

It consists of two paragraphs.

Introduction

A new generation of ocean general circulation models will have resolution small enough to partially resolve ocean mesoscale eddies, which are present throughout the ocean and are an important driving force for ocean jets. Unfortunately, eddies which have sizes similar to the grid scale model resolution can behave unrealistically, and thus need to be parametrized to account for effects of unresolved smaller-scale eddies.

One such parametrization is presented in Anstey and Zanna (2017). They parametrize horizontal eddy Reynolds stress tensor directly by computing derivatives of zonal and meridional velocity. Then, on the example of eddy vorticity flux behaviour they demonstrate that vorticity tendency is determined by interaction between different spatial scales. This then motivates the fact that small-scale eddy anisotropy can be parametrized in terms of large-scale vorticity and deformation.

We verify this claim using a well-studied quasi-geostrophic model of a two-dimensional, zonally-evolving, barotropically unstable jet. The model serves as an idealized representation of an oceanic western boundary current jet extension, like the Gulf Stream or Kuroshio Extension, downstream of where the current has separated from the coast. Our model setup has a number of advantages for this particular study: its eddy-mean flow interactions have been well-studied and are well understood; it contains a number of different eddy-mean flow interaction regimes; the nature of eddy-mean flow interactions can be systematically manipulated; and the model is inexpensive to run at spatial resolutions that well-resolve all relevant eddy scales.

Furthermore, this model specifically has regions of upgradient momentum fluxes which vorticity deformation parametrization promises to parametrize well.

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Theory

Express streamfunction in terms of Fourier series around a fixed spatial point:

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \psi_{\mathbf{k}}(t) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x})$$

Anstey and Zanna (2017) show that in this case, different spatial modes can be used to explain vorticity tendency as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{p}}^{(\kappa)}}{\partial t} \propto -2\kappa(k^2 + l^2) [pq(k^2 - l^2) - kl(p^2 - q^2)] \psi_{\mathbf{k}} \psi_{\mathbf{p}}$$

This is only on-zero if we have interactions between different spatial scales, i.e. when $k \neq p$. Hence, the remaining problem is just to find the partitioning scale that would split spatial scales in such a way so that smaller scales are parametrized by larger scales as best as possible.

To partition the field into large-scale and small-scale all we then have to do is collect parts of streamfunction associated with large and small wavelengths. We can do this for example, by applying a convolution on the streamfunction. This would essentially have the effect of picking only long wavelengths.

The actual parametrization we are investigating here is that small-scale eddy anisotropy can be approximated in terms of large-scale vorticity and deformation:

$$L = \kappa |\zeta| \delta$$

Here L is small-scale eddy anisotropy, which is computed as:

$$L = \sqrt{\frac{(\overline{u'u'} - \overline{v'v'})^2}{4} + \overline{u'v'}^2}$$

Since this is just the small-scale eddy anisotropy, the overall anisotropy will also include large-scale eddy anisotropy:

$$L = L_0 + \kappa |\zeta| \delta \tag{1}$$

Where L_0 is large-scale eddy anisotropy that can already be resolved on low-resolution models.

The other side is defined as:

$$\zeta = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \text{ (vorticity),} \quad \delta = \sqrt{D^2 + \tilde{D}^2} \text{ (deformation)}$$

Where:

$$D = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \text{ (stretch),} \quad \tilde{D} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \text{ (shear)}$$

Finally, velocities are computed from streamfunction:

$$u = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \text{ (zonal velocity),} \quad v = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \text{ (meridional velocity)}$$

We can interpret this parametrization as follows: there are different modes of eddy anisotropy and vorticity-deformation fields. On larger scales, we only detect long wavelengths. Yet, this parametrization predicts that unresolvable wavelengths of eddy anisotropy field, can, to some extent, be computed from resolved large-scale modes of vorticity-deformation field.

Now, what remains is to formalize two things:

1. How exactly large scale field is computed.
2. How exactly are means computed for eddy anisotropy.

These both points have the same solution: all we need is a way to “average” the field. Since the motivation behind this parametrization is to use it in GCM, it makes sense to treat those averages as spatial averages since they can be computed at any time step just from the streamfunction at that time.

In general, one can compute such averages as follows:

Average of a function $f(p)$ at a point $(x_0, y_0) = p_0$ is defined as:

$$\overline{f(p_0)} = \int f(p) \sigma(p_0, p) dp$$

Where we integrate over all spatial domain. Intuitively, this is just weighted average, where weights possibly depend on the position around which average is computed.

Thus, $\sigma(p_0, p)$ is a density function with the following properties:

1. $\int \sigma(p_0, p) dp = 1$
2. $\sigma(p_0, p) \geq 0$
3. $p_0 \in \operatorname{argmax}_p \sigma(p_0, p)$
4. $\lim_{\|p\| \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(p_0, p) = 0$

The first two properties basically constrain the density function to be a density function. The last two properties are motivated from physical considerations: we want most information to come from around the point around which we want to compute the sampling, and not the points that are further away.

We know that in general, densities can be described in terms of mean, variance, skewness, and even higher moments of distribution. Since we want to use this for applications where we have a notion of model grid scale size, we at the very least want the variance. Thus, the simplest distribution that we can use is a Gaussian one. The variance in this case would denote partition scale of the fields, as well as averaging scale for computing averages of small scale eddy anisotropy.

It should be noted that this might not be the best choice since it was shown that mesoscale eddies share energy in a non-local way Grooms et al. (2013).

TODO: citation to paper where they used convolution previously?

Procedure

Looking back at (1), we can treat it as a linear model when partitioning scale is fixed:

$$L = L_0 + \kappa|\zeta|\delta$$

where linear model parameters are L_0 and κ .

To proceed, we use our eddy-resolving model to (1) compute the fields, and, (2) while doing so, find optimal partitioning scale for each point in the field.

We don't impose a strict assumption that partitioning scale is the same across all locations, and later we will show why this assumption is a good one.

Before going further, we also need to understand precisely what we mean by fitting the model. After all, for a fit to be reasonable, we need more than a single data point. Hence, what we do is:

1. Select a point in spatial domain
2. Around that point, select a patch of points
3. We should expect model values to vary smoothly along the field.
4. The further away the point is from the center of the patch, the less important it should be.

More precisely, letting x_0 be the center of a patch, we minimize the function:

$$\min_{\sigma, L_0, \kappa} \int (L(\sigma|x - x_0) - L_0 - \kappa|\zeta(\sigma|x - x_0)|\delta(\sigma|x - x_0))^2 \cdot [-(x - x_0)^2] dx$$

Where the first term is the squared difference of left hand side and right hand side of the equation (1), and second term is the weight. In our experiments, we actually replace the integral by a sum, and optimize over a square patch of size $2\sigma + 1$ centered at x_0 .

It is worth noting that his optimizer is not perfect. For example, it doesn't at all detect the fact that field is smooth. I.e. we can randomly scramble points in a patch and still get the same result. In our experiments that wasn't such a big problem, but it could be a bigger problem for some applications. For example, if one cared about derivatives of eddy anisotropy more than its actual value.

Experiments

To demonstrate our point about eddy anisotropy being a linear function of vorticity-deformation field, we would first study some examples for fixed (not necessarily optimal) partitioning scales.

Model on a small patch. Since we assume that partitioning scale is not constant throughout the whole spatial domain, we first pick a small patch of instantaneous streamfunction to analyze.

Figure 1: Attempt at linear fit at a fixed partitioning scale of 9.8 at position (400,400).

Bias diagnostics. Results of this research don't change much if we pick different sampling region size, or if we make it depend on partitioning scale. Hence, for performance reasons, we can set it constant and make it not too large. It doesn't seem like there is a large bias coming from the choice of partitioning scale. True, it is slightly biased towards larger partitioning scales (i.e. ≈ 2), but that's about it.

Sampling region size is more of a modeling meta parameter choice. If we expect the field to be very smooth, we should pick larger sampling region size, and if we expect it to be very rough, we should pick a smaller one.

Model. Looking at (1), for a fixed partitioning scale, this becomes a simple linear regression problem. It is indeed linear, as seen from Figure 1. Now we just need to pick partitioning scale which works the best. In order to characterize performance of linear models, Adj. R^2 is often used.

There are two useful definitions of R^2 :

- $R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (y_i - f_i)^2}{\sum_j (y_j - \bar{y})^2}$
- $R^2 =$ Pearson correlation between y_i and $b + mx_i =$ angle between y and $b + mx$

I.e. the first one is basically one minus squared ratio of residuals by spread of original data. It is sort of like relative uncertainty, but the opposite. The closer R^2 is to 1, the better the model is. Second definition is good to know because it describes goodness of fit as if the model and original data were two vectors. If they are collinear – then model completely described the data. If they are orthogonal – then model doesn't describe the data.

Adj. R^2 is just a re-scaling of R^2 to penalize adding more variables to linear regression. The difference is not really important for our case, since we only have two parameters (slope and intercept).

Figure 2: Comparison of linear regressions for different partitioning scales at position (400,400). Maxima of $\text{Adj. } R^2$ are marked with red vertical lines, minima – with blue lines. Numerical values for maxima and minima are displayed in Table 1.

Interpretation of slope is eddy mixing rate, and intercept is large scale eddy anisotropy.

Looking for the best partitioning scale. Now that we know how to find eddy mixing rate and large scale eddy anisotropy for a given fixed partitioning scale, the next step is to figure out how to pick a good partitioning scale. To do that, we can first simply scan different reasonable partitioning scales. We do so in Figure 2.

As is seen from the plots, we get several smooth functions of partitioning scales. Furthermore, we see that there are in fact 3 maxima in $\text{Adj. } R^2$, and two minima between those, where the value of minimum goes all the way to zero. This situation actually persists for other locations in the field.

For any point there could be anywhere from 1 to at least 3 maxima in $\text{Adj. } R^2$.

Now, to get an optimal partitioning scale, we could just pick the maxima with the largest $\text{Adj. } R^2$.

Partitioning Scale	Intercept (10^{-4})	Slope (10^{-2})	$\text{Adj. } R^2$
3	1.371 ± 0.019	-0.739 ± 0.07	0.13990
4.5	2.398 ± 0.021	-0.43 ± 0.122	0.01678
10	4.795 ± 0.052	17.5 ± 0.457	0.68501
14.5	10.922 ± 0.245	13.87 ± 2.99	0.02953
18.5	24.205 ± 0.155	-53.203 ± 2.441	0.41294

Table 1: Numerical results for maxima and minima in Figure 2. We have sampled partitioning scales with a period of 0.5, so minima here are upper bounds for actual minima, and maxima – lower bounds for actual maxima.

The next step is then to rigorously study spatial distribution of these optimal maxima, and how well the parametrization performs in different dynamical regimes.

Figure 3: Test

Figure 4: Adj. R^2 for different point along the purple line from second plot of Figure 3. As we move along the line, one of the maximums grows taller and taller, and eventually optimal scales flip.

Are these flakes in partitioning scale values random noise? No, this is not the case, as we see from Figure 4, where we travel along the purple line shown on the large scale eddy anisotropy plot.

The reason we have this effect is essentially due to the discontinuity of the *argmax* function. We could have two well-defined maxima, and have one of them slowly increase in size. Then eventually *argmax* would flip to the maximum which previously was smaller of the two maxima.

Therefore, optimal partition scales will jump. This is just the consequence of the fact that we have several local maxima.

But there is still hope to get something smooth. Even though the *argmax* is discontinuous, the maxima themselves are not. Only their ordering scrambles, as we see from Figure 5.

What is the meaning of these three modes/bands of maximas? Well, if we go back and look at Figure 2, we would notice that each of maxima corresponds to a particular dynamic regime that is specified in terms of eddy mixing rate.

Eddy mixing rate could be close to zero, positive, or negative. And each of those maxima maps to a particular choice of eddy mixing rate. In other words, vorticity deformation field either drives eddy anisotropy up/down, or doesn't affect it at all.

Discussion

Meaning of partitioning scales. We can understand the results using the following analogue. Let u and v be two vectors, that represent eddy anisotropy and vorticity deformation. Next, let $\{e_1, e_2, \dots\}$ be a basis in which we will express these vectors. In terms of Fourier modes, the first vector would describe larger wavelengths, and the vectors that follow will describe smaller and smaller wavelengths/spatial scales.

Figure 5: Several domains of optimal partitioning scales. We see that we have three different dynamical regimes: (1) positive eddy mixing rate, medium partitioning scale, medium large-scale eddy anisotropy; (2) negative eddy mixing rate, large partitioning scale, large large-scale eddy mixing rate; and (3) small eddy mixing rate, small partitioning scale, small large-scale eddy anisotropy.

We can roughly now think of our spatial averaging function as some operator that takes both fields/vectors u and v , and only keeps the first n basis vectors.

And then we compute the fit by taking inner product between these two vectors. Hence, for “partitioning scale” of n , we get the following value for fitness:

- $u = \sum_i u_i e_i$
- $v = \sum_i v_i e_i$
- $\langle u, v \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^n u_i v_i$

Notice that we allow arbitrarily dimension for u and v , but in the inner product, we cap the sum at n terms.

We can also think about this geometrically. Say we have two vectors and a line. Even if these two vectors are orthogonal, if the line forms a 45° angle with these two vectors, then projections of these two vectors inside the line will be collinear.

But then, if these two vectors say live in 2d, if we were to add just one more dimension to the space we project to, the inner product would once again become zero.

Conclusions

Acknowledgments

Temp

TODO

- *TODO*: We will make the field smaller in the final version, so red rectangle will be larger
- *TODO*: replace scatter plot by density plot
- *TODO*: fix field parametrization plot for overall field
- *TODO*: add residuals plot for overall field
- *TODO*: add absolute residuals plots for patch and overall field (1 - “rel. residuals”/“actual value”)
- *TODO*: add a fitting & try to understand if there is a unique optimal partitioning scale. Analyze how well the general linear relationship performs for different partitioning scales. Does it help if we add dynamic information (i.e. assume things shouldn’t change too much in time?)
- *TODO*: Later work: analyze how well derivatives of field fit? I don’t think those would fit that well...
- *TODO*: replace correlation by weighted one?
- *TODO*: T-value is just inverse of relative error. Should we keep it? Visually it does kind of look differently
- *TODO*: have a plot of sampling kernels for several partitioning scales on top of psi mean? Just to demonstrate what scales are “reasonable”.

Understanding Experimental Results

Fitting model analytically. From above, we get:

$$u(x, y) = \int \partial_{y_0} \psi(x_0, y_0) g(\sigma|x_0, y_0|x, y) dx_0 dy_0$$

$$v(x, y) = - \int \partial_{x_0} \psi(x_0, y_0) g(\sigma|x_0, y_0|x, y) dx_0 dy_0$$

Where $g(\sigma|x_0, y_0|x, y)$ is our averaging function with partitioning scale σ .

References

Anstey, J., Zanna, L., 2017. A deformation-based parametrization of ocean mesoscale eddy reynolds stresses. *Ocean Modelling* 112, 99–111.

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